

GREEN ECONOMY AS A PATH TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Аннотасија. Мақоллада яшил иқтисодийотга о‘тиш, барқарор ривожланishga erishish, davlatimiz rahbarining ekologik tashabbuslari, iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning yangi past uglerodli modeliga o‘tish, iqlim o‘zgarishiga qarshi kurashish bo‘yicha aniq chora-tadbirlar, energiyadan oqilona foydalanish, qazilma boyliklardan bosqichma-bosqich voz kechib, yashil texnologiyalar foydasiga hal etish masalalari o‘rin olgan.

Калит со‘злар: yashil iqtisodiyot, ekologik tashabbus, "Yashil Makon", chiqindilarni qayta ishlash, tabiatni muhofaza qilish, ekologik ta'lim va tarbiya.

Аннотация. В статье освещаются вопросы перехода на зеленую экономику, достижения устойчивого развития, об экологических инициативах Президента нашей страны, перехода к новой низкоуглеродной модели экономического развития, о конкретных мерах по борьбе с изменением климата, рационального использования энергии, постепенного отказа от ископаемых ресурсов в пользу зеленых технологий.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, экологическая инициатива, «Яшил макон», переработка отходов, охрана природы, экологическое образование и воспитание.

Abstract. The article covers issues of transition to a green economy, achieving sustainable development, environmental initiatives of the President of our country, transition to a new low-carbon model of economic development, specific measures to combat climate change, rational use of energy, gradual abandonment of fossil resources in favor of green technologies.

Key words: green economy, environmental initiative, "Yashil Makon", waste recycling, nature conservation, environmental education and upbringing.

Many countries around the world are switching to a green development course today. These processes are caused by climate change, environmental pollution and depletion of natural resources. The increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere leads to global warming, and this is the main factor provoking extreme weather events, melting glaciers, and temperature anomalies. The transition to a green course implies a complete transformation of the economy and public life and involves abandoning traditional, carbon-intensive energy sources in favor of environmentally friendly and renewable ones. The concept covers not only the energy sector, but also industry, transport, agriculture, education and medicine.

The Paris Agreement, for example, sets out the need for specific measures to combat climate change, forming a turn towards a new low-carbon model of economic development based on the gradual abandonment of traditional technologies for the extraction, processing and use of fossil resources in favor of green technologies. Uzbekistan, having joined the Paris Agreement, has undertaken obligations to curb global warming. Thus, by 2030, our country plans to reduce specific greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 35 percent compared to the 2010 level. Climate change has negative impacts on food, environmental, energy, social and economic security.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that the transition to a green economy and achieving carbon neutrality are strategic priorities for the New Uzbekistan. And this is not only an environmental, but also a socio-economic necessity. Our country has significant reserves of natural resources, and the transition to more sustainable methods of their use can contribute to economic growth and job creation. The importance of the green course is also due to the fact that sustainable development contributes to improving the quality of life and health of the population, and helps reduce poverty.

The environmental initiatives of the President of our country, presented at UN venues, receive broad support from the international community and make a real contribution to ensuring sustainable development at the global level. On August 13, 2024, the UN General Assembly, at the initiative of Uzbekistan, adopted a Resolution on promoting sustainable forest management. The document calls for participation in the implementation of tree planting projects on degraded lands, including in drylands, and to ensure the long-term conservation of planted trees by developing effective care strategies. The adoption of the resolution is an act of international recognition of the success of the implementation of the national project “Yashil Makon” and the large-scale initiative to green the dried-up bottom of the Aral Sea. Based on the initiatives of the population, the creation of "green gardens" and "green public parks" is initiated at a cost not exceeding 250 million soums. Funds allocated annually from the State Budget are directed to the creation of: - arboreturns, dendrological and botanical gardens in each region; - "green belts" around cities and districts;

- large gardens with an area of at least 5 hectares;
- "green shields" to reduce the impact of transboundary dry winds and dust and sand storms;

- growing seedlings on the basis of home-based farming on 1.5 thousand hectares of forest land in 2024; - as an experiment, tree passports in the city of Tashkent through their digitalization within the framework of the national project "Yashil Makon"; - planting trees on the roadsides in at least 5 rows; - providing the opportunity to use a portion of the grown trees, not exceeding 30 percent per year, for industrial and construction purposes; - holding an annual competition "The Greenest Mahalla", as well as rewarding 14 mahallas, which became winners according to the results of the competition, at the expense of the Ecological Fund.

More initiatives have been put forward at the national level. Here, the emphasis is on the development of renewable energy. The total potential of solar and wind energy in Uzbekistan is 10-12 times greater than the current volume of energy consumption. In total, 10 green power plants (nine solar and one wind) have been commissioned in the republic since 2021. From January to October 2024 alone, the amount of electricity produced by all solar and wind power plants in our country amounted to 4 billion kWh. The results of green energy production allowed saving 1.2 billion cubic meters of natural gas and preventing emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere in the amount of 1.6 million tons. At the same time, this volume of electricity is equal to the annual social norm for 1.6 million households. Currently, 25-30 percent of the total electricity produced in Uzbekistan comes from solar, wind and hydroelectric power plants. It is expected that by 2030, more than 40 percent of the total electricity generated will be produced through the commissioning of green power plants. This will allow us to save 25 billion cubic meters of natural gas annually, and most importantly, reduce harmful emissions into the atmosphere by 34 million tons. Among the most important initiatives aimed at developing a green economy, it is worth noting the programmatic measures to improve energy efficiency: in 2024, the law “On energy saving, its rational use and improving energy efficiency” was adopted.

The nationwide project “Yashil Makon” cannot be ignored. The large-scale initiative to create green space involves planting a billion trees and shrubs over five years, or 200 million trees and shrubs per year. The results of this truly national project will contribute to improving air quality, combating climate change and desertification, fulfilling obligations under the Paris Agreement, and most importantly, improving the standard and quality of life of people.

It is also impossible not to touch upon the topic of environmental education. In order to form an environmental culture from an early age, courses dedicated to issues of sustainable development and careful attitude to nature are being introduced in kindergartens and schools of the country. Engaging young people and raising their awareness of the impacts of climate change are of paramount importance for the state’s long-term adaptation policy. In 2019, the Concept for the Development of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted, the purpose of which is to form environmental knowledge, awareness and relevant culture in the younger generation. It is aimed at improving science in the field of ecology using innovative technologies, improving the qualifications of specialists in the field of education and environmental protection.

The main directions of the country's green policy are enshrined in program documents aimed at preserving natural resources. For example: a separate article on environmental protection was introduced into the 2023 Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, long-term strategic documents have been adopted. These are the Concept of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (aimed at ensuring environmental safety and reducing the negative impact on nature), The concept of development of water management in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 (includes measures for the rational use of water resources), Strategy for the management of solid municipal waste in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2019-2028 (involves the introduction of modern waste disposal and recycling systems, which will improve the sanitary condition of cities).

Uzbekistan has introduced new mechanisms that ensure the practical implementation of green development principles in business. For example, from June 1, 2023, a “green certificate” system will be in effect, ensuring environmental standards at the production stage, and from January 1, 2024, a monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) system will be in effect to control all types of greenhouse gases. It aims to provide public access to monitoring data, reporting and climate change adaptation processes.

Uzbekistan has demonstrated impressive growth in the implementation of water-saving technologies (WST). Thus, over the past five years, the area covered by these technologies has increased by 7.7 times, reaching one million hectares. These results brought Uzbekistan into the top 10 world leaders in terms of the area of implementation of VST, occupying 7th place, second only to such countries as Israel, the USA, Russia, Spain, Brazil and Italy.

The share of renewable energy in the country's energy balance will increase to 30-40 percent, and its production will reach 25 thousand megawatts. It is expected that in the next three years, 28 large solar and wind power plants with a capacity of 8 GW will be launched in Uzbekistan. Switching to renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, will significantly reduce the country's carbon footprint. And restoring ecosystems, including greening the Aral Sea region and other regions, will improve biodiversity and mitigate the effects of climate change. Efficient use of water resources, including through the introduction of drip irrigation, will help us cope with droughts, desertification and water shortages. Water consumption will decrease by 25-30 percent due to the introduction of modern technologies, particularly in agriculture. And

the development of eco-tourism will help to raise the standard of living in the regions. The transfer of urban public transport entirely to environmentally friendly fuel will lead to an improvement in the environmental situation in cities, and cleaner air, water and environmentally safe food will have a positive effect on the quality of life of the population.

On April 4, the International Climate Forum opened in Samarkand under the theme “Central Asia in the Face of Global Climate Challenges: Consolidation for Common Prosperity”. The forum brought together leaders of Central Asian countries, the leadership of the European Union, representatives of the UN and other international organizations, as well as experts, scientists, activists and representatives of youth movements. The aim of the forum is to promote the development of coordinated regional solutions in response to growing climate risks and environmental threats. This event was held within the framework of the Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy in Uzbekistan and continues the climate initiatives announced in recent years.

In his speech, the leader of Uzbekistan linked climate problems with food and energy security. More than 20% of the region's land is subject to degradation, and without the necessary measures, crop yields could decrease by a third within 25 years. In this regard, he proposed to combine scientific efforts within the framework of the Horizon Europe program to increase the sustainability of the agricultural sector. Special attention was paid to the issues of transition to a "green" economy and the development of renewable energy sources. In the next five years, Uzbekistan plans to increase the share of energy obtained from renewable energy sources to 54%, which will reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 16 million tons. The President confirmed Uzbekistan's commitment to fulfilling the obligations under the Paris Agreement - reducing emissions by 35%.

Green development thus has the potential to become a key factor for sustainable economic growth.

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